

Geomorphic evolution of the Miage Lake: a morphometric evaluation of the changes from 2018 to 2024

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Abstract — The Miage Glacier, located on the Italian side of Mont Blanc, features the popular touristic Lake Miage. This lake has experienced significant changes in recent years, including a Glacial Lake Outburst Flood (GLOF) in July 2022. This study uses geomorphometry to analyze the lake's evolution and increasing hazard. Comparing photogrammetric surveys (2018, 2022, and 2024), changes were tracked in the lake's volume. In 2018, the lake held 170,000 m³ of water, with a potential capacity of 340,000 m³. By 2022, the volume increased to 450,000 m³. In 2024, the actual volume was 137,000 m³ and the potential volume decreased to 210,000 m³. These changes highlight the complex role of factors influencing the lake's dynamics, including glacier flow, ice melt, and debris input. Continuous monitoring is crucial to understanding these evolving processes including the natural risks that can affect the area.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Miage Glacier is a debris-covered glacier located at the bottom of the Italian side of Mont Blanc (Val Veny, Courmayeur, AO). On the right flank of the glacier there is the Miage Lake, an important touristic site, due to its landscape value and also because of its location along the famous “Tour du Mont Blanc” trekking route [1–4] (Fig. 1). In recent years, a series of different proglacial lakes originated in the area, with seasonal life, filling up during the spring and emptying in the summer, remaining full for varying periods annually.

Figure 1. View of the whole Miage Glacier (helicopter photogrammetry, 2022). The Miage Lake is empty after the event of July 11, 2022.

Lake Miage - empty after July 2021 – starting on June 2022 fills up reaching maximum flooding level in early July 2022, culminating at about 2006 m a.s.l. (Fig. 2). Thereafter, a weak eastward overflow occurred during the night of July, 11 when the sudden emptying of the lake generated a Glacial Lake Outburst Flood (GLOF). Flood propagated within the endoglacial conduits until it escaped from the front of the South Lobe; the ejection of pressurized water resulted in the collapse of the latero-frontal moraine at several points. The occurrence of a GLOF made it essential to monitor the Lake sector in order to better understand the evolution dynamics of the area to be able to make a proper assessment of environmental hazard characters. In this work, we want to bring into attention the role of geomorphometry for interpreting the recent evolution of the lake, the increase in volume that can be stored in it, and the increase in hazard that afflicts the Miage Glacier area.

Figure 2. Miage Lake as seen from the NE. At its maximum fill level, reached in early July 2022, the lake filled the entire depression to a natural overflow level on the downstream side. Photo courtesy by F. Pollicini

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

In the context of Glacial Monitoring carried out by the Italian Glaciological Committee (CGI), the Miage Glacier is one of the glaciers with the largest amount of data collected over the years. In particular, the sector related to Lake Miage was particularly studied over the past few years. Since 2018, photogrammetric surveys of Lake Miage was carried out, first by drone photogrammetry, and later by photogrammetric helicopter flyovers. In this paper, 3 datasets obtained from Structure from Motion (SfM) [5,6] photogrammetry shown in Table 1 are compared.

TABLE I. TECHNICAL DETAILS OF THE CAMERAS USED IN THE SURVEYS

Cameras used in photogrammetric surveys				
Survey year	Camera type	Sensor type	Focal length [mm]	Mega pixel
2018	DJI Phantom 4 Pro	CMOS 1"	8,8	20
2022	Sony a6400	APS-C	16	24.2
2024	Sony a6400	APS-C	16	24.2

Photogrammetric surveys were georeferenced using Groud Control Points (GCPs) acquired by geodetic GNSS systems in order to obtain the best possible coregistration among the obtainable products. Therefore, each survey was processed in Agisoft Metashape [7] in order to obtain detailed Digital Surface Models (DSMs) and orthophotos. In this work we compare the dataset presented in table 2 in order to quantify the modification of the Lake Miage

TABLE II. DETAILS OF THE PHOTOGRAMMETRIC SURVEYS (PERFORMED WITH EMPTY LAKE)

Dataset		
Year	Product	Resolution [cm]
August 2018	DSM	20
	Ortophoto	5
August 2022	DSM	26
	Ortophoto	13
October 2024	DSM	20
	Ortophoto	10

The products obtained were compared in a GIS environment to identify the levels of water recorded and contained in the reservoir in 2018, 2022 (the lake was filled to the maximum possible), 2024 (Fig. 3) and that potentially contained in 2018, 2024.

Figure 3. Miage Lake as seen from the NE. At its maximum fill level, reached in early June 2024, two lakes filled part of the whole depression. Photo courtesy by P. Deline

III. RESULTS

The image datasets were analyzed individually. In 2018 the erosional notch generated by waves into the ice cliff was clearly visible, indicating the lake’s settling level (2006 m a.s.l.). That level was maintained by the lake until it was completely drained (in August). Both notch line and the DSM of the empty depression of the lake allowed to calculate the actual volume of the lake (170’000 m³) and the potential volume, achievable if the whole lacustrine basin were full (340’000 m³). Shifting to year 2022, we consider the lake being full before its complete emptying as a result of a GLOF. The highest possible “closed” contour line were used to calculate the volume of the lake depression: 450’000 m³. Finally, the same process was carried out for 2024 in order to obtain the volume reached by the lake (137’000 m³) and the maximum potential value (210’000 m³). All the geomorphometric results are summarized in Tab. 3.

TABLE III. POTENTIAL AND REACHED DIMENSIONS OF THE LACUSTRINE BASIN OF MIAGE LAKE

Miage Lake			
Year			Dimension
2018	Reached	Area	18’000 m ²
		Volume	170’000 m ³
		Water height a.s.l.	2006 m
	Potential	Area	25’000 m ²
		Volume	340’000 m ³
		Water height a.s.l	2014 m
2022	Reached and Potential	Area	33’000 m ²
		Volume	450’000 m ³
		Water height a.s.l	2006 m
2024	Reached	Area	16’000 m ² (two lakes)
		Volume	137’000 m ³
		Water height a.s.l	1990 m
	Potential	Area	22’000 m ²
		Volume	210’000 m ³
		Water height a.s.l	1994 m

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

According to the interpretation of dataset created by means of photogrammetric surveys, The Miage Lake area is spreading in time span 2018 – 2022. Possible causes of this expansion are: the accelerating rates of erosion on the ice cliffs that surround the Lake; the decreasing velocity of the glacier itself preventing the ice cliff advance. Therefore, the geomorphological equilibrium of the Lake sector was broken creating a much larger depression, more than 130% increase from 2018 to 2022 (Fig. 4). But the contraction of the glacier and the lowering of the whole surface led to a progressive reduction in the area that can potentially be filled. Additional factors contributing to determine the reduction in volume of the Lake are: the accumulation of debris carried by ice and the landslide of the moraine at the southern lake shore.

As result, the shape, the depth and potential invadable volume of the lake are the result of a complex dynamic balance between many factors: glacier flow velocity, ice melt and debris input from the glacier and moraine. Concerning the amount of water in the depression, both potential (fig. 5A) and reached level (fig. 5B), it is affected by snow and ice melt rates, precipitation, incoming/outgoing endoglacial water flows, and finally by stress conditions within the glacier that result in the opening or closing of endoglacial conduits. An example of the effects of the morphoevolutive dynamics on the southern ice cliff is shown in figure 5. These processes are in continuous changing due to climate change and it is hard to predict future shape of the lake area. This work emphasises the importance of continuous monitoring of the area in order to better understand and control the changes can occur in the Lake Miage area in order to reduce the multiple potential risk (GLOF, moraines instability, ice falls, ...) that can born in the area.

V. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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Figure 4. Detail of the area of Miage Lake. It is observable the evolution of the maximum dimension of the lake's basin through the time.

Figure 5. Topographic profiles of the Ice Cliff bordering the lake downstream. It is possible to appreciate the eastward migration of the cliff and the lowering of the surface downstream. Furthermore, Dashed lines show the potential level of water (A) and the reached level of water (B) in each investigated year. The location of the profile is shown in Figure 4.